

Preliminary Spatial Analysis on the Water Quality and Water Problems of Kalaw City

Kay Thwe Hlaing*

Thida Lwin**

Abstract

This paper is a spatial analysis on water quality and water problems of Ward No.6 and Ward No.1 in the Kalaw City, Shan State. Groundwater from shallow aquifers is widely used as a water resource of the Kalaw City but its groundwater has some chemical problems in the study area. There are; also not only water quality problems but also there are water shortage problems for water utilization in the summer season. To use safety groundwater for health, it is important to make clear the actual conditions of physical and chemical characteristics of groundwater in this area. Water samples are collected at 38 measurement points of groundwater in the dry season. Water quality analysis included pH, temperature, Electricity Conductivity (EC), Salinity and Total Dissolve Solids (TDS) are checked using Water Quality Test in the field survey and making structured survey for checking water shortage problems in the study area. There are some water shortage problems and poor water quality in the study area because of its location and increasing population in the study area.

Keywords : groundwater quality, pH, Electricity Conductivity, Total Dissolve Solids and Salinity

Introduction

Myanmar is rich water source but the study area is not enough for water utilization and water quality of shallow aquifer is also not well because of its location. There is no specific agency which has the budgetary mandate of authority to have initiatives of water resource management. In the study area where has some chemical problems in the groundwater, rain water collection systems are used in the raining season. Water supply systems in Kalaw City cannot guarantee the water quality good for drinking, as existing water treatment facility is incapable. Therefore it is important to make clear the actual conditions of physical and chemical characteristics of groundwater in this area to use safety groundwater for health. Hlaing, et al., 2007 reported the results of a preliminary study of water quality of the Ayeyarwady, Myanmar but there are no previous study about water quality and water utilization results in the study area. Most of researchers from Myanmar Geography Department studied about land use in the Kalaw Area.

Regional Setting

The study area is situated on the northern part of the Kalaw City in the southern Shan State. Kalaw City is located between 20°24' 23" and 21°2'45" North Latitudes and 96°25' 58" and 96°51' 20" East Longitudes and it is above 4315 feet mean sea level. Kalaw City is far 42 miles from Taunggyi City and 58 miles from Tharsi Town. Kalaw City is about 3.74 square-miles. There are eleven wards in the Kalaw City and it is bounded by Taunggyi on the east, Nyaungshwe in the south and, Pindaya on the north.

* Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Geography, Bago University.

** Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Geography, Bago University.

Figure 1 Location Map of the Study Area (a. Shan State in Myanmar, b. Kalaw in Shan State, c. Ward No. 1 and d. Ward No.6)

Topography of Kalaw City is generally mountainous area and some parts are valleys. Especially mountains are bounded on the east and north east of the city. The main river is Kalaw Creek in the study area and it is flowing from Sin Taung and enters into the Inlay Lake. There are no permanent rivers in the study area.

Figure 2 Relief Map of Kalaw City

According to the climatic records, the average monthly temperature is about 13.46° C and the annual rainfall is 21 inches respectively. The climate of Kalaw urban area is Humid Subtropical “Cwa” type of climate according to the Koppen’s Climate Classification method. The maximum annual temperature is 26.09° C and the minimum annual temperature is 13.64° C (1995-2015). The mean annual temperature is 19.86° C. April is the highest temperature of 22.91° C and January is the lowest with 14.51° C. There are fogs especially in January. Kalaw is

situated on the mountain slope of the Eastern Highland of Myanmar; it receives more rain than the surround regions. The mean annual rainfall of Kalaw for the period from 1995 to2015 is 48.90". August is the month with the largest amount of rainfall (9.36") and January is month with the lowest amount of rainfall (0.07) in Table 1 and Figure 3.

Table 1 Annual Temperature and Anural Rainfall of Kalaw City (1995-2015)

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Average /Total
Maximum Temp (°C)	23.8	26	29.4	30.3	26.8	26.37	25.7	25.7	25.8	26.44	24.3	23.5	26.09
Minimum Temp (°C)	5.27	7.02	11.2	15.5	17.8	18.32	18.4	18.3	17.4	15.68	12.1	7.09	13.64
Mean Temp (°C)	14.5	17	20.3	22.9	22.3	22.34	22.1	22	21.6	21.06	18.2	15.3	19.86
Rainfall (inches)	0.07	0.4	0.47	2.13	5.76	5.82	7.87	9.36	7.31	6.09	3.33	0.31	48.9

Source: Meteorology and Hydrology Department, Taunggyi.

Figure 3 Climate of Kalaw City (1995-2015)

Material and Methods

Water samples are collected in the study area from 29th April to 02nd May 2016. Most water samples (the ground water) were taken with a plastic bottle from wells and some water is domestic water for using house holds in the study area. They were collected in plastic bottles in 29th April to 02nd May 2016, and were measured through temperature, pH, Electric Conductivity (EC), Salinity and Total Dissolved Solid (TDS) using water quality analyzer in the field survey and we checked some water utilization problems, are obtained by structured interviews and questioner survey with the selected local people and mainly from the departments concerned.

Photo 1. Water Samples Collection in the Field Survey (30th April, 2016)

Results

Water Pipeline Systems in the Study Area

Kalay City's peoples are depending mainly on four sources to water supply- Ye-Aye-Pond, Innbyin Pond, Thithtwin Pond and KhanaukSein Pond. In the study, mainly water source is Innbyin Pond where is distributed by using 2inches (PVC) pipeline system and four water storage tanks. This pipeline is connected 8" and 6"pipeline, after reaching Two Lions Mountain. Water is supplied to people living in Wade No.1 and 6 by pumping system, water is not enough for both of hilly area and the lowland land area of study area. Therefore, most of the study area is facing water shortage problems in the summer and water quality problems throughout the year. The main source of water in the study area is directly derived from ground water. According to the field survey within the Ward No.1 and 6, water supply system is carried out by municipal pipeline system. The most household are using the water from the municipal pipeline.

Figure 4 Water Pipeline Systems in Kalaw City

The water supply cost is given by dwellers. Water one unit is limited 100 kyats. At least one hour has been given ten thousand kyats per month. Some dwellers have no pipeline connected system, they are depending on the private water sellers. The municipal pipeline water from Innbyin Pond sent to four tanks which located in the Ward No.1. This water supply system is one time one hour per two days aiding public pipeline. Innbyin Pond is located about one mile away from the northeastern part of Kalaw City. It is 164 feet wide and 4 feet deep, and second largest pond of the Kalaw. Innbyin Pond is distributed by using the 4 inch pipeline system. During the rainy season, the amount of available water in Innbyin Pond is 15000 gallons per hour and 12500 gallons per hour in summer. Water from the pond is firstly pumped up by using three water pumps and then sent to the tank on Two Lions Mountain. It

can store 180000 gallons. Water is provided to Ward No.1 and Ward No. 6 and other wards by gravity flow system. Water from Innbyin Pond is distributed to Ward No. (7) Via the 4 inches pipeline system in Fig.4.

Photo 3 Innbyin Pond where is located in the eastern part of Kalaw City.

Source: Photos are taken from Field survey in 30th April, 2016

Photo 4 Pipe lines which supply water to the study area.

Analysis for the Basis Water Quality of the Water Samples

The results of water quality information especially temperature, pH, EC, Salinity and TDS are obtained by measuring in the field survey in 2016. We checked GPS point for all

water samples and install in the ArcGIS10.22 using geodatabase. Then spatial distribution maps for each elements are drawn using each water quality results in Fig. 5 (a to e).

The lowest temperature is 21.5 °C and the highest is 34.2°C due to the field observation time and the depth of aquifer of the study area.

The lowest pH concentrations is in the drinking water of the study and the highest concentrations of pH occur in the wells of settlement areas of the study area with pH values ranging between 6.32 mg/L and 9.14 mg/L with an average value of 7.91 mg/L.

The lowest EC value was 197.6 μS/cm and the highest was about 625μS/cm. The most deteriorated and salty water was in shallow aquifer from Inpyin Water Source of the study area with an average EC in the private groundwater wells of 483.42 μS/cm.

Salinity in the groundwater has three to six times higher than the WHO standards. The highest are 302 mg/L from well water and the lowest are 96.3 mg/L from tube-well in the study area.

Figure.5(a) Water Temperature of the Study Area

Figure. 5 (b) pH Values of the Study area

Figure. 5 (c) Electricity Conductivity Values of the Study Area

The highest total dissolved solids are 443 mg/L and the lowest is 142 mg/L for the drinking water with average of 343 mg/L in the study area.

Figure. 5 (d) Salinity Values of the Study Area

Figure. 5 (e) Total Dissolved Solids Values of the Ward-6

Water Utilization Problems of the Study Area

The water utilization conditions and water problems are checked using questioner survey and structured interview in the study area in the field survey. Then water problem related living people are analyzed using statistical method referenced by Microsoft Excel. There are 38 samples for households in the study area. Among the 38 household, total number of household is range from 2 to 8 persons in the study area. Occupation of Head of Household (80%) has jobs and 20% are job less. Total worker in a household are from 1 to 5 persons and number of dependency are from 2 to 5 persons. Most of dependency is females. Income for one month of household ranged from 120000 kyats to 800000 kyats and some are good income. Expenditure for one month are 150000 kyats to 500000 kyats.

Most of living people in the study area are native and some are migrated from other cities because of their kinship. Costs of water utilization for household per month are 5000 to 20000 kyats. Their main water sources and water services facilities are community tube well tank. Most of people are using public pipeline and community tanks from Innpyin Pond and they cannot get the water available 24 hours a day. They receive the water one time in two days from public pipeline and community tank. 75% of households usually obtain drinking water and 25% households have to buy drinking water. 90 % people do not see the public pipeline in their street. 90% households are satisfactory the quality of water from community tube-well and tank water coming from public pipeline. Their perceptions on water quality condition of present and previous ten years ago in the township are very fair.

Discussion and Conclusion

The study area is located in the northwestern part of the Kalaw City. The main sources of water in the study area are directly derived from ground water. Most of water samples in the study area are not so good for drinking water from WHO standard because of study area's location (limestone area). The some test result outcomes are (pH value of water sample higher than permissible limit of WHO Standard). The EC value is quite good in the water source area (Innpyin Area) but the water from settlement area is a little high because of water treatment (Chlorine).

The municipal pipeline system in the study area is not enough if we compared with household number. Some household do not have pipeline water directly from water tank to their home. Therefore the new water supply system is very important role for the development of the study area.

There are also water shortage problem in the every summer season because the study area have not enough the water storage tanks and well systematic pipe line. Most of household must spend for drinking water so they can not save money for other purposes. The problem of water quality part is also important because their water quality is not satisfied enough. Therefore they must use hot water for drinking.

Table 2 Water Quality Analysis Results from Field Survey in the Study Area

Code	long	Lat	Temp	pH	EC	TDS	Salinity
K-1	96.53528	20.66556	27	8.04	602	425	291
K-2	96.56463	20.64228	24.6	7.86	197.6	141	96.3
K-3	96.55908	20.60353	22.5	6.32	625	443	302
K-4	96.55896	20.637	21.5	6.62	416	297	200
K-5	96.55926	20.63664	27	7.93	535	380	260
K-6	96.55918	20.63661	26.3	8.09	530	376	262
K-7	96.55923	20.63645	26.8	7.92	550	392	268
K-8	96.55941	20.63639	26.8	8.12	533	378	258
K-9	96.55943	20.63638	26.3	8.14	473	338	230
K-10	96.56223	20.63764	27.5	7.43	577	412	285
K-11	96.55739	20.63987	24.9	7.96	553	393	263
K-12	96.55663	20.64011	23.9	8.86	515	366	245
K-13	96.55811	20.63931	25.4	7.99	530	377	260
K-14	96.55669	20.64209	24.7	8.07	495	349	239
K-15	96.55623	20.64153	27.6	8.04	343	246	167
K-16	96.55401	20.63685	25.1	8.01	514	368	253
K-17	96.89292	20.59632	33.8	7.91	388	276	189
T-1	96.56505	20.6385	28.6	7.25	595	423	288
T-2	96.56518	20.63847	28.6	8.16	430	306	208
T-3	96.56499	20.6383	28.5	7.95	575	406	279
T-4	96.56452	20.6384	28.4	7.93	522	371	254
T-5	96.56445	20.63813	28.7	8.18	455	322	220
T-6	96.56422	20.64058	28.7	8.26	410	291	198
T-7	96.56374	20.63748	27.9	7.38	586	418	286
T-8	96.56953	20.63909	23	7.94	557	396	270
T-9	96.56967	20.63946	29.1	7.79	562	402	273
T-10	96.56979	20.63997	29	7.94	483	345	234
T-11	96.56981	20.64079	29.1	7.86	566	405	276
T-12	96.57027	20.64084	29	7.75	550	392	268
T-13	96.56944	20.64165	29.2	7.81	507	362	248
T-14	96.56942	20.64157	29.1	7.85	601	427	293
T-15	96.56768	20.63977	28.1	7.51	595	420	285
T-16	96.56702	20.6405	27.7	7.76	466	335	226
T-17	96.56783	20.64034	28	7.2	618	437	300
T-18	96.56776	20.64091	28.2	8.24	523	374	253
T-19	96.56804	20.64153	28.1	8.26	471	336	228
T-20	96.56869	20.64099	28.4	8.27	479	338	231
T-21	96.56825	20.64097	28.3	8.21	450	321	218

Acknowledgements

The author would like to express gratitude to Dr Min Aung, Adjunct-rector, Bago University and Professor Dr. Min Aung Pann, Head of Geography Department, Bago University for constant encouragement and providing opportunity for publication of this paper.

References

- Kay Thwe Hlaing, Aye Aye Mauk, Shigeko Haruyama. (2014). *Development of Land Utilizations and Water Quality for Hlaingtharyar Township in Yangon City*. Myanmar, Japan: TERRAPUB, Tokyo.
- Kay Thwe Hlaing. (2012). *A Preliminary Assessment on the Surface Water and Groundwater Conditions in the middle Part of the Ayeyarwady Delta, Myanmar*. Jour. Myan. Acad. Atrs & Sc., Vol. X, No.6.
- Makiko Senda, Kay Thwe Hlaing, Kunihide Miyaoka, Shigeko Haruyama and Yasuhisa Kuzuha. (2014). *Water Environments in the Southern Delta of Myanmar during the Rainy Season*. Journal of Japan Society of Civil Engineers.
- Senda, M., Kuzuha, Y., Kay, T. H., Miyaoka, K., Haruyama, S. (2011). *Research on Water Environment in Myanmar*. Proceedings of 2011 Annual Conference of the Japan Society of Civil Engineers, September 7-9, 2011 Ehime, Japan, 66, VII-20, VII39-40, DVD, 2011 (in Japanese).
- WHO: *Guide lines for drinking-water quality*. fourth edition, pp. 1-541, 2011.